

JURISPRUDENCE

LEGAL ASPECTS OF NORMS REGULATING THE ECOLOGICAL FIELD

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Abstract

As we know, after our country regained its independence, along with all other areas, a new environmental policy was formed in the field of environmental protection, as well as a foundation was created for the full provision of people's rights to live in a healthy environment. During the time when the great leader Heydar Aliyev was the head of Azerbaijan, as in all fields, the issues of solving environmental problems were always in the center of attention. Special attention was paid to the improvement of the ecological situation, environmental protection, including the efficient use of natural resources.

Keywords: ecological, modernization, green world, factor, anthropogenic, rational, bioresource, object, reasonable.

After Azerbaijan gained its independence in 1993, a number of "forest, land, water, etc. laws have been passed. Effective state policy aimed at the development and modernization of Azerbaijan is always successfully implemented. Successfully continuing the socio-economic policy defined by the great leader Heydar Aliyev, President Ilham Aliyev pays special attention and care to the ecological situation of our country in his activities. It is no coincidence that the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan signed the Decree dated December 25, 2023 on the declaration of 2024 as the "Year of Solidarity for the Green World" in the Republic of Azerbaijan. Our country has been designated as a clean environment and green growth country until 2030. Enhancing the environment, restoring and increasing greenery is a task incumbent on our country and its citizens.

When talking about environmental crimes, the first factor that needs to be mentioned is the environment [1]. The environment is understood as the totality of animate and inanimate nature that surrounds it, regardless of human activity. The environment includes both the natural environment and man-made objects to meet its social needs, as well as natural-anthropogenic objects. Environmental protection is included in the nature protection and social functions of the state and its local self-government bodies. Environmental protection is provided by state and municipal bodies, social and political parties, and business participants for the purpose of favorable, rational use and restoration of natural resources.

Environmental protection is regulated by legislation. Violation of these norms is regulated by various legislative acts depending on the level of public danger of the illegal act committed in the national legislation.

In accordance with Articles 14 and 39 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the rights to natural resources and living in a healthy environment are declared. It is no coincidence that the provisions related to the environment are specified as both a constitutional right and a duty in the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Thus, in Article 39 of the ARK, the right to "live in a healthy environment" is reflected as a right of everyone, and in Article 78, "protection of the environment" is assessed as the duty of every person. In Article 39 of the Constitution, the right to live in a healthy environment is attributed to everyone, not every citizen. Therefore, this right applies to all citizens, foreigners and stateless persons living in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan. It should be noted that the right to live in a healthy environment is attributed to the human factor, i.e. everyone, in the duty of environmental protection mentioned in Article 78. In addition to these, the laws "On environmental safety" and "On environmental protection" were approved by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on June 8, 1999 in the field of environmental protection. The purpose of the mentioned laws is to ensure environmental safety and prevent harmful effects on the environment.

Environmental offenses are cases that create an obstacle to environmental protection. Therefore, there are special chapters on environmental law violations in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Code of Administrative Offenses. Chapter 28 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan is devoted to environmental crimes. The criminal offenses included in that chapter are as follows:

Article 247: Violation of environmental protection (protection) regulations during the execution of works; Article 248: Violation of the rules of circulation of environmentally hazardous substances and waste; Article

249: Violation of veterinary rules and rules of control against plant diseases and pests; Article 250: Pollution of water (water sources); Article 251: Pollution of the atmosphere (air); Article 252: Pollution of the marine environment; Article 253: Violation of the legislation of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the coastal shelf; etc.

The basis of the application of the law in nature protection activities is the norms of the criminal legislation in force. In accordance with the requirements of the law, the application of the law in the field of nature protection was carried out by the court, prosecutor's office, internal affairs bodies, nature protection inspectorates, state control and management bodies. The history of the development of the national criminal legislation also allows us to say that the application of the law in the field of environmental protection is a state power activity carried out in a special form determined by nature protection and other areas of legislation. This activity consisted of the implementation of control over the actions of relevant persons carried out by the relevant authorities and public organizations and compliance with the requirements of the nature protection rules, as well as the implementation and following mandatory measures by the state against subjects who violate those rules. In other words, due to the entry into force of the new Criminal Code, the most recent development history of the National criminal legislation of Azerbaijan has acquired modern and effective criminal law tools and mechanisms in the fight against environmental crimes. Chapter 23 of the Law No. 678-IQ dated June 8, 1999 of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Environmental Protection" is entitled "Responsibility for Violation of Environmental Protection Legislation, Dispute Resolution".

Article 78, called "Responsibility for Violation of Environmental Protection Legislation", states: "Legal and natural persons guilty of violating environmental protection legislation, including officials, are liable in the cases provided for in the Civil, Administrative Offenses and Criminal Codes of the Republic of Azerbaijan."

The Code of Administrative Offenses of the Republic of Azerbaijan was approved by Law No. 96-VQ dated December 29, 2015. Chapter 25 of the Code is called administrative offenses against the rules of environmental protection, use of nature and ecological safety, and 42 articles have been established in this chapter.

The overlapping of environmental interests and economic interests in society requires the protection of both of them. This raises the issue of environmental responsibility along with economic responsibility. Serious environmental irresponsibility is equated with environmental crime. A number of normative acts have been adopted in the field of environmental crimes. A number of conditions must be met in order for an environmental offense to be considered a criminal act. Article 7 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan states that only a person who is found guilty of a socially dangerous act (action or inaction) and its consequences can be brought to criminal responsibility and punished [3]. A person cannot be held criminally responsible for the damage caused by his innocence. The scope of which socially dangerous acts are considered

as crimes is determined by the criminal legislation. Only a person who has committed actions or omissions prohibited by criminal law may be held criminally liable. There can be no criminal liability without a criminal legal fact. That is, the assessment of the fact as a socially dangerous act and as a crime can only be determined by the composition of the crime. The concept of criminal composition is directly provided for in the criminal law. According to Article 3 of the Criminal Code, only the commission of an act (action or inaction) in which all the signs of the criminal composition provided for by this Code are present creates criminal responsibility. As we mentioned, the scope of socially dangerous acts of a criminal nature is determined by the criminal law. It is in the norms of the special part of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan that the composition of each crime exists. In this regard, the criminal composition exists regardless of the subject's will. By committing a crime, the signs of the crime are voluntarily adjusted to the signs provided for in those norms, and it is clarified that the act is a crime, and at the same time, what kind of crime it is. Each crime has its own characteristics. However, there are signs in those crimes that it is the object that suffers damage as a result of all crimes, the person who caused damage to the object intentionally or carelessly, by action or inaction. If we summarize from this point of view, it becomes clear that the constituent signs of the crime are divided into objective and subjective signs. Thus, the composition of a crime is a set of objective and subjective signs that characterize a socially dangerous act as a crime, provided for in the criminal law [5]. As for specific environmental crimes, the composition of those crimes should be understood as the sum of the objective and subjective signs, which characterize the environmentally dangerous act as a crime, provided for in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Depending on the objective and subjective signs of the crime, there are 4 signs of the composition of the crime. These are the following:

1. The object of the crime
2. The objective side of the crime
3. Subject of the crime
4. The subjective side of the crime

Public relations protected from criminal intent by the criminal law constitute the object of the crime. In other words, the object of the crime is the social relations damaged as a result of the crime [4]. The main object of environmental crimes is the effective use of natural resources protected by the criminal law, maintaining a quality environment for people and living things, and social relations in the field of ensuring the environmental safety of the population. The direct object of these crimes is social relations in the field of protection and efficient use of various resources of nature and ensuring environmental safety of the population [2]. One of the objective signs of environmental crimes is the objective aspect of the crime. The objective aspect of the crime refers to the external aspect of the socially dangerous act. Objectively, the action of the subject of the environmental crime must be illegal. Legal freedom manifests itself in two forms. Active – violation of environmental legislation. Passive – failure to comply with the requirements of the law. The subject

of the violation is the rules of environmental law (system of legal relations). Environmental law violation is characterized by three signs: 1) illegality of the act; 2) environmental damage or real threat of environmental damage, or violation of other legal rights and interests of environmental law subjects; 3) the presence of a causal relationship between the illegal act and the infliction of environmental damage or the real threat of such damage, or the violation of other legal rights and interests of environmental law subjects. In criminal law, the distinction between external and internal aspects of the act serves for a deeper assimilation of these tools. This sign of the objective aspect is reflected in the disposition of the matter in all cases. Pursuant to Article 19 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan, an adult who has committed a crime under the age limit defined by the Criminal Code shall be held criminally liable [3]. Article 20 of that code states that the age limit for criminal prosecution is sixteen. It should be noted that in Article 20.1 of the criminal law, the subject in a number of crimes was listed as fourteen years old instead of sixteen years old. According to Article 20.2 of the Criminal Code, a person who has reached the age of fourteen is only guilty of intentional homicide, intentional minor or serious harm to health, kidnapping, rape, acts of sexual violence, theft, robbery, smuggling, and threats, illegally seizing a car or other means of transport without the intention of looting, intentionally destroying or damaging property in aggravating circumstances, terrorism, taking hostages in aggravating circumstances hooliganism, stealing firearms, ammunition, explosives and devices or threatening shall be criminally liable for solicitation by fear, robbery or solicitation of narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances, and making vehicles or roads in an unusable condition. Apparently, environmental crimes do not belong to this type of crime, so the subject of this crime must be a person who has reached the age of 16. However, the fact that a person who has committed an environmental crime reaches the age of sixteen does not mean that he is still a subject. In Article

19 of the Criminal Code, another sign of the subject is that it is understandable. A person who was in an irrational state at the time of committing an environmental crime, i.e. a person who did not understand the actual nature and public danger of his act (action or inaction) or was unable to control it due to chronic mental illness, temporary impairment of mental activity, mental retardation or other mental illness, shall be criminally liable not involved. Environmental crimes can be subjectively defined as intentional or reckless. If a person realized that his act (action or inaction) is socially dangerous, foresaw its socially dangerous consequences and desired them, or realized that his act (action or inaction) was socially dangerous and foresaw its socially dangerous consequences, but if he did not desire them and consciously allowed such consequences to occur, in this case the crime will be considered to have been committed intentionally. As a result, it can be concluded that environmental crime is a socially dangerous, relatively massive and stable socio-legal and psychological event that harms the natural environment and human health or creates a threat of harm.

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